

**GROWING INTEREST IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN
PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN WITH THE HELP OF GAMES.**

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Abstract: This thesis describes the methods of teaching English to preschool children. Now English is becoming a world language. Therefore, it should be started from preschool age. The thesis provides information about this.

Keywords: foreign language, words, atmosphere, rule, song, cartoon, intellectual, methodology, speech, games, interesting handouts.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In order to further develop the study of foreign languages, our honorable president made many decisions, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" and at the same time "The preschool education system until 2030" development concept " was approved. These decisions reflect issues such as further development of the network of preschool education system, use of modern and effective methods of teaching children, provision of preschool educational institutions with qualified personnel, preparation of children for school education. It is not an exaggeration to say that the further development of the education sector is one of the urgent areas that our government is paying attention to today.

In the last few years, learning a foreign language has become a necessity rather than a way of self-development. A foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional pre-school educational institutions. The demand for a foreign language in society, on the one hand, as well as the understanding by parents that language is not only a factor in the education of a modern person, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society, on the other hand, this moment encourages early learning of a foreign language, especially popular and make relevant. If 20 years ago knowledge of a language was required only in certain fields of work, now it is necessary to master at least one. The main problem of teaching a foreign language is the age of the student. It is known that children are more comfortable to learn. Until recently, teaching methods were aimed at children. Now parents are trying to start learning a

foreign language as early as possible. The main goals of teaching preschool children a foreign language:

- formation of children's basic communication skills in a foreign language;
- the ability to use a foreign language to achieve one's goals, to express one's thoughts and feelings in life communication;
- creating a positive attitude to further study of foreign languages;
- arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries. Preschool age is especially favorable for starting to learn a foreign language. Children of this age are distinguished by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experiences, the "secrets" of language.

It is necessary to pay attention to children and find out their interests with various questions such as quizzes and picture tests. After talking with each child and determining their interests, we start the lesson with suitable songs, games, interesting and colorful multi-character handouts that attract attention. First of all, we greet the children and before we explain our topic, we conduct small conversations with the children about our topic, listen to their opinions, and start with songs and games about our topic. Because it is easy and interesting for children to develop an understanding of the subject and to understand the lesson. We will gradually distribute our interesting distributions. We will also distribute it with a game. For example, we can ask children about their favorite color or their favorite cartoon characters. After distributing the handouts, we slowly explain the topic by asking them what they imagined when they saw it. Young children can be easily distracted. We entertain them with various games so that they don't get bored quickly. Types of games to keep them from getting bored:

Mirror game - the purpose of the choice is to develop children's observation and attention.

There is also a game called "Find the mistake". The purpose of choosing this game is to determine whether the child has understood the lesson. For example, today's topic is teaching how to say numbers in English. We place the numbers in the picture in different ways and show them to the children and ask them to find the mistake. If we teach children in sequence, for example, they will say. We can tell if they understand the subject by the mistakes they make.

Our next interesting game is this - if we are teaching numbers in our topic, we will show a picture with numbers and ask the children which number it is.

In the process of "Sound Tale" children look at pictures together with the teacher and at the same time pronounce words. "Cartoons in English" is one of the best assistants in teaching English. Children love cartoons and enjoy watching them back to back. Therefore, cartoons in English help to solve many problems of teaching children a foreign language at the same time. • Subject environment; If the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, the children will learn the language better. For example, traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the subject of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) will give. This method strengthens students' vocabulary, language abilities, and expands their worldview. Teaching songs and rhymes about letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember and have no meaning. For example, it can be shown that children learning the English alphabet by singing is more effective than simply memorizing. Games involving mental and physical activity. cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

Using songs and action games to improve the classroom environment. Creating a flexible classroom atmosphere is sometimes more important than any teaching method. In the class, at the beginning of the lesson, with a nice English song, all the children, led by the teacher, sang together and danced a little to the tune. This in itself will help them exercise their bodies, become more energetic and memorize the lyrics of the song faster. The English environment, importantly, allows for a natural entry into a good learning atmosphere. Children's self-control is weak, and it is difficult for them to concentrate and hold their attention during the whole lesson. Therefore, the teacher should provide songs that children like to listen to, poems or quick sayings to practice the language, or if not, an animated cartoon that children like.

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should be conducted as an interesting activity, not as a duty, and using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. The importance of learning foreign languages should be properly explained to children through natural conditions. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi knew many foreign languages perfectly, could speak them easily and created in them. Such an opportunity motivated scholars to study world

science and do great things. After all, as our grandfather Navoi said, "He who knows the language - knows the world."

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